

THE IMPORTANCE OF EXTRA-CURRICULAR ACTIVITIES OF GENERAL
SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

Ramazonova Guzal Mukhammadovna

Master of Fine and Applied Arts Department of Bukhara State University

Azimova Muhayo Barotovna

Bukhara State University Associate Professor of Fine and Applied Arts Department (scientific leader)

Abstract: This article talks about the meaningful organization of students' free time, the importance of extracurricular activities and types of extracurricular activities in their development as a well-rounded person.

Key words: Circle, spiritual activities, tasks, integration, curricular and extracurricular activities

Currently, a number of effective decisions and laws are being adopted in the education system of our country. In his address to the nation on December 20, 2022, President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev stated the need to teach schoolchildren foreign languages and professions. At the meeting held on January 20, 2023, it was planned to train students in 64 different professions based on the characteristics of districts and neighborhoods. In today's rapidly developing era, such decisions are timely for the meaningful organization of students' free time and the development of tourism in our country. There are several types of clubs that fully cover extracurricular activities:

- scientific circles;
- circles of skilled hands;
- carpentry circles;
- sports club;
- artistic amateur circle.

In secondary general education schools, these activities are organized by the head of the class and the organizer of educational activities. The head of the class closely supports the leaders of the circle. He invites his students who have the same interests and aspirations to join a club.

Extracurricular activities supplement the educational activities of students. They help them to form a correct worldview and moral maturity. It creates the ground for the close connection of theoretical knowledge with practice and production. The duties of the organizer of extracurricular activities include:

- ❖ control planning and implementation of extracurricular educational activities;
- ❖ to organize multifaceted extracurricular activities of students with the help of pedagogical team, class activists of student organizations;
- ❖ providing methodological support to teachers, class leaders, parents, student organizations, class activists while directly guiding the direction of extracurricular activities;
- ❖ participation in the most important educational events held at the general school and between schools;
- ❖ extensive use of educational and cultural institutions and public power in organizing students' free time;

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The educational effect of extracurricular activities depends to a large extent on the level of organization of the educational process and how the students organize various tasks as a team member. Extracurricular activities are not limited to the compulsory program, but the youth unites various students voluntarily.

He carries out work on the basis of their initiative, makes them interested in science, brings them into the environment of the cultural life of the people.

Extracurricular activities are the most important factor in the formation of social activity, social consciousness and moral habits in a person. This activity includes the works of the scientific community, literary and school theaters, readers' conferences and discussions on various topics, lectures and conversations on political, moral, scientific-popular and labor topics, social and useful work, political information, holiday evenings and mornings, to includes training sessions.

Extracurricular activities of students are considered to be a means of thinking and attitude according to their content. Because the information obtained during extracurricular activities is perceived, processed and new knowledge is created on this basis.

Students participate in extracurricular activities, interact with different people, and face different tasks. Therefore, the more diverse the students' activities, the richer their relationships, the wider the range of relationships, and the more effective their spiritual growth. In educational activities outside the classroom, students learn to work in a team, feel the joy of social work, join production work, get used to obeying public opinion and fighting for the honor of the team. Extracurricular activities are determined according to the spiritual and physical development and age characteristics of the participants. This process is also influenced by the conditions of the school where they are studying. Although the tasks of all schools in our country are the same, they have their own characteristics, and these characteristics are clearly visible in cultural and national conditions.

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